

Development of Natural Hemp Fibre Sheet Mould Composites (NF- SMC)

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Abstract

The use of natural fibres as reinforcement in polymer composites has generated much interest in recent years due to environmental legislation and improvements on natural fibre performance and process-abilities. This research investigated the use of natural hemp fibre as reinforcement for the possibility of producing fibre reinforced Sheet Moulding Compounds (SMC) as an alternative to glass fibres in the industrial applications ranging from building construction, automotive, to aerospace, where a good fire performance and mechanical properties are essential. This work shows that NFSMC achieved equivalent level of fire and mechanical properties that glass fibre SMC (GFSMC) has provided. Its Heat Release Rate (HRR) in the fire reaction tests reached 150 kWm^{-2} which is better than that of fire retardant GFSMC; tensile strength reached 44 MPa and Yang's modulus in excess of 14 GPa, which are as the same as the high performance polymeric GFSMC.

This report was worked on two aspects of the NFSMC: the selections of raw materials, formulation and a suitable manufacturing system; and the material characterisation and functionality.

Key words: Natural fibre, Hemp, Sheet Moulding Compounds, SMC, composites

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Introduction

The use of natural fibres has been documented worldwide dating back over 3,000 years before any industrialised development. And the amount of its usage was significantly reduced since early 1970's due to the high-tech synthetic fibre development (such as polyester, Nylon, and glass/carbon fibres) and their superior mechanical properties. The development and application of natural fibre polymer composites have been extensively reviewed [1,2,3]. However, with the current increasing in environmental concerns, energy saving and the economical issues, the natural fibres are once again being considered to be a preference as reinforcements for polymeric and cementation composites as well as many other applications^[4,5]. In this work, hemp fibre applications in Sheet Moulding Compounds (SMC) were used as a major reinforcement in polyester resin system and in its manufacturing technologies. The motivation was to investigate the feasibility of using the natural fibre as an alternative to glass fibre for the SMC in the applications of building construction, automotive and aerospace where good fire performance and mechanical properties are required.

SMC composites are widely used in building/construction, transportation (automotive, vehicles, rail, etc), chemical/petrochemical industries, Electrical sector, etc. In 2007, the world production of SMC was over 1 Million tonnes, and its market value was worth more than £1 billion. The SMC conventionally uses man-made glass fibre or carbon fibres as reinforcements with good mechanical properties, durability (life cycle time is around 30-50 years depending on the environments) and fire performance. However, these have produced a huge challenge for recycling^[6,7,8].

Current development on natural fibre composites based on published information is mainly on press moulding, injection moulding for thermoplastics, etc^[9,10,11]. Some of them are using pure thermosetting resins without additional filler; and some others are using large amount of fillers incorporated into thermosetting resins (i.e. Phenolics, unsaturated polyester and vinyl ester resins). However, the research works of natural fibre composites developed in this paper have been concentrated on developing suitable manufacturing formulation for the SMC/DMC processes, improving fire performance and impact resistance.

Raw materials and SMC preparation

From the manufacturing process trials as shown in Figure 1, hemp fibre SMC can be produced with a traditional SMC fabrication machine with modified matrix formulation. The fibres were impregnated in the process and then the pre-preg sheets were hot pressed. Testing results showed significant improvement in mechanical properties with the incorporation of popular fillers such as CaCO₃ and ATH which also enhanced the functionality, mechanical properties and improved fire resistant, in particular reduced the materials cost by overall 15%.

Figure 1. NF-SMC sheet for moulding and an SMC production machine in running using natural hemp fibre.

1) Natural fibres:

The use of natural fibres in the UK, especially Hemp which is commonly grown in the surrounding areas of London, has been well known for thousands of years- being used to manufacture simple ropes and bagging fabrics. Even many places were named after Hemp (Hempstead, Hemel Hempstead, in the North London area, etc). Figure 1 shows a natural fibre role as compose of randomly orientated chopped fibres. The natural fibre and fibre mat showed in Figure 2 were produced by Hemcore Ltd, a company based in Cambridge, UK.

Figure 2. Natural fibre chopped form and mat form.

2) Resin paste/matrix system and sheet preparation and composite moulding

A standard SMC resin formulation normally contains 100 parts orthophthalic polyester resin, chemical initiator, inhibitor and Zn-type release additive, etc. All the basic resin paste mixture was carried out on a low to high speed mixer (0-200 RPM) as shown in Figure 2. The basic SMC formulation can be tailored into functionalised application systems by using various fillers such as calcium carbonate (for surface finishing and low cost), antimony trioxide or Aluminium Trihydrate (ATH) for fire retardancy, Wollastonite or Talc for stiffness, improved mechanical properties, etc.

The developed natural fibre composite manufacturing process in this work is shown in Figure 3 on the processing SMC machine. And a fast composite moulding process is schematically shown in Figure 4. And in the work, SMC polyester resin pastes were provided by Menzolit Composite Group, with general paste and fire retardant paste. Their formulations are listed in Table 1.

Figure 3. Small scale mixing head for producing small amount of resin systems and schematic and lab view of the SMC production and machine (Central and right).

Figure 4. A Schematic representation of the moulding process of natural fibre SMC/DMC.

Viscosity reduction is expected during moulding at the temperature around 140 °C – 190 °C while the compound flowing into the mould cavity to form expected shape.

Table 1. SMC and Fire retardant SMC paste:

Composition	Normal formulation (Parts)	Fire retardant formulation (Parts)	%
Orthophthalic resin	70	70	33
Polystyrene (40% sol)	30	30	14
Fillers	100 (CaCO ₃)	100 (ATH)	48
Zn Stearate	5	5	2
TBPB	1.2	1.2	0.6

Mechanical tests

Mechanical tests (Tensile and Flexile) tests of hemp fibre reinforced composite samples were carried out according to ASTM D3039. The composite specimens were prepared with end taps to prevent failure close to the grips. The dimensions of the tensile specimens were 220 mm × 25 mm with an average thickness of 3.0 mm. The gage length was 140 mm. The tensile test was performed on an Instron 6025 universal tensile testing machine. The cross-head speed of 1 mm/min and a load cell of 30 KN were used.

Fire tests

To assess the fire performance, the NFSMC was subjected to Cone Calorimeter (CC) tests, which is considered particularly valuable for studying material thermal resistant variables. The CC was developed for small-sample tests compared with other testing methods such as a normal scaled furnace test (i.e. BS476 Part 20) ^[12,13]. The information about inherited thermal properties of the materials can be collected from CC through applying different degrees of thermal heat flux, which reflects a material's basic thermal reaction to heat radiation ^[14,15,16,17]. In the work, all the materials were tested at the same condition under the heat flux of 75 kW/m², as shown in Table 2. An example of the test for composite plate and a test of SMC sample under tests in the CC are also shown in Figure 5. Here, as the fire performance is probably a single most important aspect to consider for the use of the all SMC's, therefore, when using natural fibre as reinforcements, the fire performance becomes more significant especially where the civilians are involved ^[18,19,20]. It is therefore important to study and understand the effect of the fire conditions of the NFSMC materials.

Table 2. SMC composite samples for fire testing.

Reinforcement Matrix	Fibre Volume fraction	Thickness (mm)	Fire test Heat flux (kW/m ²)
Fire retardant Glass fibre SMC	30	5.0	75
Fire Retardant Hemp SMC	40	5.0	75

Results and discussion

Mechanical properties

There have been always issues with the low mechanical properties and fire performance of natural fibre composites before 2000. And since then, performance of natural fibre SMC (NFSMC) has been improved tremendously. Characterisation of the NFSMC materials when started the project in 2005 gave that the average mechanical properties of the NFSMC were over 20% lower compared to glass fibre SMC. In end of this work in 2008, the NFSMC

achieved maximum tensile strength 44 MPa and Yong's modulus 12 GPa from original tensile strength 24 MPa and modulus 7-9 GPa.

Fibre surface treatment also improved mechanical properties

The mechanical properties of a fibre reinforced composite are governed in part by the transfer of stress between fibre and matrix. For natural fibre composites the interface between the fibre and matrix is weak due to the incompatibility of the hydrophilic cellulose fibre that partially covers the hemp with waxy substances on the surface, and the hydrophobic matrix. Therefore, in this investigation two primary different surface treatments were employed.

- 1) Alkalisiation: natural fibres were treated firstly with an alkaline solution. The treatment removed the waxy substances on the fibre surface thereby improving the close contact of fibre-matrix.
- 2) Silane treatment: the treatment increased interfacial bonding. One of the reactive groups forms chemical bonds with an inorganic substrate with $-OH$ groups such as the fibre, while the other end group contains double carbon chain ($-C=C-$) reactive groups forming the chemical bonds to the polymer resin (with $-C=C-$, etc).

Table 3 shows mechanical properties of general glass fibre SMC (30 % wt.), Hemp SMC (26-30 %(wt.) without treatment, Alkali treated Hemp SMC and Silane treated Hemp SMC. It is obvious that the values of mechanical properties of the SMC's with treated Hemp fibre were generally increased 1.7-1.8 times and most encouragingly, even surpass the properties of glass fibre SMC's.

Table 3. Mechanical properties of glass fibre and natural fibre SMC

Property	Glass SMC	Hemp SMC	Alkali treated Hemp SMC	Silane treated Hemp SMC
Tensile Strength (MPa)	35 MPa	27.5 ± 4.7	44.2 ± 1.6	41.3 ± 4.00
Tensile Modulus (GPa)	12 GPa	14.4 ± 8.2	19.8 ± 6.7	15.9 ± 2.1
Flexural Strength (MPa)	70 MPa	56.5 ± 6.3	84.1 ± 3.0	77.2 ± 3.1
Flexural Modulus (GPa)	7.0 GPa	5.7 ± 0.4	7.5 ± 1.0	8.5 ± 0.8

Fibre treatment for fire properties:

The feasibility of using natural fibre SMC has been hindered by the flammability of natural fibres. However, when the NFSMC was exposed to the heat flux, the first event was the decomposition of the resinous part, followed by the exposure of the fibres to fire, which resulted in the composite structure being rapidly consumed in the flame, while evolving considerable quantities of heat and smoke.

In order to improve this performance, different fibre surface coating techniques were employed. For example, surface coatings containing ammonium polyphosphate (APP), boric acid (BA), borax solutions (BS) and others (were used to treat the natural fibre materials.

Coating the fibres with different technologies for the SMC was proved to improve the flame retardant properties. The samples moulded from SMC with coated fibres by both materials had shown a dramatic decrease in heat release rate as shown in Table 4. In Figure 6, a NFSMC plate and its fire test using a Cone Colorimeter were shown. Samples were cut on to the dimension of 100 × 100 mm. All tests were carried out in accordance with ASTM E1354. Samples were pilot ignited and run in triplicate.

Moreover, it normally contains absorbed moisture, the amount of which will vary according to the relative humidity and conditions of exposure. The rate of heat transfer in a hygroscopic

material is significantly influenced by the evaporation of any physically or chemically entrapped moisture ^[16].

Unlike synthetic polymers, natural fibre and wood type materials are an inhomogeneous material which is also anisotropic. It is a complex mixture of natural polymers of high molecular weight ^[18,19], the most important of which are cellulose (~50%), hemicelluloses(~25%) and lignin (~25%) ^[15], although these proportions vary from species to species. Thermodynamic data of aluminium trihydrate shows it absorbing as high as 1.20 MJ/kg of thermal energy by the following reaction:

Figure 6. Specimen before testing with Al foil as stated by ASTM E1354; General view of the Cone Calorimeter during a test (right).

Table 4. Heat release rate of glass SMC, fire retardant glass-SMC, NFSMC, and treated fire retardant NFSMCs.

Specimen	Peak Heat Release Value (kW/m ²)
NFSMC (Non-Fire Retardant Natural Fibre SMC)	361
SMC (Non- Fire Retardant)	333
FRSMC (Fire retardant SMC)	204
FR NFSMC	179
10% APP FR NFSMC	143
7% BA+7%BX FR NFSMC	131

FRSMC is the fire retardant glass fibre SMC.

APP = ammonium polyphosphate

BA = Boric acid

BX = Borax

FR NFSMC = fire retardant Natural Fibre SMC

The natural fibre fabrics were sprayed with this formulation before pressing the SMC.

The methods of the treatment were documented on treating wood fibre, etc but not for treating natural fibre for the composite applications.

The FR NFSMC had a peak heat release value of 179 kW/m², which was a great deal better than that of a synthetic FRSMC which had a value of 204 kW/m². However, when the hemp fibre mat was coated with an FR solution the peak heat release dropped further to 131 kW/m² for the best samples, which were much lower than those of current industrial FRSMC. One of the hidden values for the natural fibres is the coating on the hemp fibre, thus causing them to char much more, which adds an extra flame retardant mechanism to the NFSMC.

Conclusion

Natural fibres, as a good replacement of glass fibres in the SMC composites have been investigated in this research, including raw materials selection, formulation, manufacturing and moulding processes and the mechanical, thermal and physical characterisations. The original proposal was on natural and wood fibre reinforced SMC for improving fire and mechanical properties especially impact resistance of the composites. For example, the impact energy absorbed by the hemp SMC ranged from 18 J to 25 J depending on volume fractions of the hemp fibre without any treatment to the fibres. The resulting materials can be preformed to give better or similar properties to that of the standard glass fibre SMC in both mechanical and general fire properties.

After the natural fibre surface treatment the result data showed that in combination of additional fillers (i.e. CaCO_3 and ATH), the treatment can significantly increase the energy absorption and fire performance as high as 50%. Though the surface treatment to the hemp fibre, the SMC gave tensile strength over 40 MPa and Yang's modulus in excess of 14 GPa. By using CC data showed that the natural fibre composites after the fibre treatment, the HRR reduced to 140 kWm^{-2} as average, which is as good as fire retardant glass fibre SMC.

The future works in Hertfordshire will be concentrated on using of natural fibre surface treatments in a better combinations of fossil fuel based resin system and natural resin systems, aiming improving their mechanical and thermal resistance performances ^[21,22].

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